

STUDIES ON THE CHEMISTRY OF RHENIUM. PART I. COMPLEX

OXALATES OF QUADRIVALENT RHENIUM

BY DEBABRATA SEN AND PRIYADARANJAN RAY;

It has been found that the tetrapositive rhenium combines with oxalic acid to form a complex acid, aquo-tri-hydroxo rhenioxalic acid, $H[(OH)_3 \cdot Re \cdot C_2O_4 \cdot H_2O]$, which slowly changes in aqueous solution into the dibasic form, $H_2[(OH)_4 \cdot Re \cdot C_2O_4]$, tetrahydroxo rhenioxalic acid. The values of the two successive dissociation constants, k_1 and k_2 , as determined by potentiometric titration, are 7.94×10^{-3} and 1.02×10^{-5} respectively. Alkali, alkaline earth and many heavy metal salts of both the forms of the acid have been described. Measurement of the magnetic susceptibility of the disodium salt gives a diamagnetic value. This is rather unusual for quadrivalent rhenium with an odd number of electrons, either in a simple or a complex compound. The phenomenon seems to suggest Re—Re metallic bonds.

Besides the well known and the most stable septivalency, rhenium exhibits a fairly stable stage in its quadrivalent condition. In this state it gives rise to complex halides of the type, $R_2[Re X_6]$ where R = a univalent metal atom and X = Cl, Br or I (Briscoe, Robinson and Stoddart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2263; Krauss and Dahlmann, *Ber.*, 1932, 65B, 877; Krauss and Steinfeld, *Ber.*, 1931, 64B, 2552; Schmid, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 212, 187). The metal also forms fairly stable oxycyanides in its quinquevalent state (Klemm and Frishmuth, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1937, 230, 215). It was therefore expected that the element might also form complex oxalates, particularly in view of the occurrence of similar oxalates formed by the neighbouring elements tungsten and osmium. Experiments carried out with this end in view have led to the successful preparation of complex oxalates of quadrivalent rhenium.

By the dissolution of freshly prepared ReO_2 in oxalic acid, a complex acid of composition, $ReO \cdot C_2O_4 \cdot 3H_2O$, was obtained. The three molecules of water could not be removed without the decomposition of the substance itself. It can therefore be represented as a complex acid of the constitution $H[Re \cdot (OH)_3 \cdot C_2O_4 \cdot H_2O]$ or $H_2[Re \cdot (OH)_4 \cdot C_2O_4]$. This is supported by the potentiometric titration of its aqueous solution by an alkali, which indicates that the acid behaves primarily as a monobasic one, but gradually changes into a dibasic form. In solution it therefore exists in equilibrium between the two forms as shown below :

On titration with alkali, the neutralisation occurs before two equivalents of alkali are added for each molecule of the acid; but if the solution is allowed to stand, the p_H continues to fall due to the formation of the dibasic form. This is evident also from the p_H —neutralisation curve, which shows a sharp rise on rapid titration before second neutralisation point, indicating that the neutralisation of the second hydrogen ion is not an instantaneous process. If, however, the titration is slowly carried out allowing sufficient time for the attainment of equilibrium after each addition of alkali, the sharp rise of the curve occurs at the proper place corresponding to the neutralisation of two H^+ ions.

The dissociation constants k_1 and k_2 of the acid H_2X , where $X = [Re \cdot (OH)_4 \cdot C_2O_4]^{2-}$ were calculated from the following deductions :

Let 'a' be the molar concentration of the total acid taken and titrated against a carbonate-free alkali of known strength, so that

$$a = a_2 + a_1 + a_0 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where a_2 , a_1 and a_0 are the respective molar concentration of H_2X , HX' and X'' ; and let 'b' be the molar concentration of the alkali added. Then from a consideration of electrical neutrality of the solution, concentration of the positive ions may be equated with that of the negative ones, that is, of $b^+ + \text{H}^+$ with $\text{X}'' + \text{HX}' + \text{OH}'$

$$\text{or } b^+ - \text{OH}' = 2a_0 + a_1 - \text{H}^+.$$

(alkali consumed) (acid neutralised)

$$b + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}' = 2a_0 + a_1 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where $(b + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}')$ is the amount of H^+ disengaged. Now, as the neutralis place stepwise, it may be assumed that when,

$$(b + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}') < a; a_0 \text{ is negligibly small.}$$

$$\text{i.e., } a_0 \rightarrow 0.$$

Therefore, from equations (3) and (4) we get,

$$a_1 = b + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}',$$

$$a_2 = a - b - \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}'$$

$$k_1 = \frac{a_1 \times [\text{H}^+]}{a_2} = \frac{[b + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}'] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[a - b - \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}]}$$

Again when $(b + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}') > a; a_2 \rightarrow 0$,

Then from the equations (3) and (4),

$$a_0 = b + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}' - a$$

$$a_1 = 2a - b - \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}'$$

$$k_2 = \frac{a_0 \times [\text{H}^+]}{a_1} = \frac{[b + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}' - a] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[2a - b - \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}]}$$

The average hydrogen ion bound to X'' at any time,

$$\bar{n} = \frac{2a_2 + a_1}{a}$$

By plotting \bar{n} against p_H , the values of k_1 and k_2 may be extrapolated from the corresponding values of p_H

$$\text{when } \bar{n} = 1.5, \quad k_1 = [H^+]$$

$$\text{and when } \bar{n} = 0.5, \quad k_2 = [H^+]$$

(Bjerrum, "Metal ammine formation in aqueous solutions", P. Hasse and Son, Copenhagen, 1941).

The values of k_1 and k_2 obtained for the rhenioxalic acid at 26° are respectively 7.94×10^{-3} and 1.02×10^{-5} .

It might be pointed out here that the value of k_1 may also be regarded as the dissociation constant of the monobasic form of the acid, *i.e.* of aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalic acid. The first neutralisation is, however, never indicated by the curve under any condition, as the k_1 and k_2 values do not differ much. The acid is obviously stronger than acetic acid and is nearly as strong as oxalic acid.

In aqueous solution at low temperatures the acid occurs mainly in the monobasic or aquo-trihydroxo form. The freezing-point measurement shows that it dissociates mainly into two ions.

Under suitable conditions the various salts of the monobasic and of the dibasic acid have been prepared and their properties studied. The molar conductivity of the sodium salt at 25° of the monobasic acid and of the dibasic acid are 110 ohms⁻¹ and 210 ohms⁻¹ respectively, which are in good agreement with those for a uni-univalent and a uni-bivalent electrolyte.

The sodium salt of tetrahydroxo rhenioxalic acid has been found to be diamagnetic though it contains a tetrapositive rhenium. A tetrapositive rhenium should possess $75 - 4 = 71$ electrons around its nucleus, with 3 of these unpaired in the 5 *d* level. In an octahedral coordination with d^2sp^3 bonds, as in the present case, these three unpaired electrons in the 5 *d* level would remain undisturbed, giving rise to a paramagnetic moment of about 3.85 Bohr magnetons, on the basis of Bose-Stoner's rule. The diamagnetic character of the rhenioxalate complex therefore suggests the formation of metallic bonds between rhenium atoms in a dimeric ion of the complex, as shown below :

The occurrence of a small temperature-independent paramagnetism in many simple rhenium compounds including ReO_2 examined by Schüth and Klemm (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, 220, 193), as also in several rhenium complexes of ter- and pentavalent compounds (Klemm and Steinberg, *ibid.*, 1936, 227, 193; Klemm and Frishmuth, *ibid.*, 1937, 230, 220) furnishes a strong evidence in support of the tendency of the rhenium atom to form metallic bonds. The rhenioxalic acid complex has been derived from quadrivalent rhenium, and ReO_2 constitutes the starting material for its preparation. There is therefore every likelihood of the Re—Re metal bonding to occur in the rhenioxalic acid and its salts. The comparatively high value found by the cryoscopic method for the molecular weight of disodium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate in solution seems to support this idea (*vide* experimental part).

EXPERIMENTAL

Scherring Kahlbaum's potassium perrhenate was used as the source of rhenium in all the preparations.

I. *Aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalic Acid*.—Potassium rhenichloride was prepared from $KReO_4$, KI and concentrated HCl (Schmid, *loc. cit.*) and recrystallised from the same acid.

From potassium rhenichloride, black ReO_2 was obtained by treatment with an excess of caustic soda solution. The dioxide was filtered and washed thoroughly with distilled water, keeping it always under water to prevent oxidation.

ReO_2 (1 mol.) was refluxed in a round bottomed flask with an excess of oxalic acid (4 mols.) solution for about 2 to 3 hours, when all the ReO_2 dissolved giving a brown solution. The solution was then cooled, filtered and evaporated to dryness over sulphuric acid in vacuum. The dried product was then washed several times by decantation with pure dioxane (dried by refluxing with metallic sodium and distilling at 102°) to remove any excess of oxalic acid. It was then dried in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid in vacuum.

The substance forms a black crystalline powder. It is highly soluble in water giving a deep brown solution. The solution reacts acidic. It is quite stable in acid medium but is readily decomposed by the addition of alkalis with the separation of ReO_2 .

Rhenium was estimated as nitron perrhenate after removal as ReO_2 , and oxalic acid in the filtrate by titration with permanganate solution after previous precipitation as calcium oxalate. {Found: Re, 48.83; C_2O_4 , 23.12; H_2O (by loss at $110-115^\circ$), 9.43. $H[Re.(OH)_3.C_2O_4.H_2O] \cdot 2H_2O$ requires Re, 48.95; C_2O_4 , 23.15; H_2O , 9.47 per cent}.

{Found (for the product dried at $110^\circ-115^\circ$): Re, 54.05; C_2O_4 , 25.51. Calc. Re, 54.07; C_2O_4 , 25.58 per cent}.

Cryoscopic measurement.

Wt. of the subs. taken (anhydrous, g./25 c.c.)	$\Delta t.$	M.W. (found).	M.W. (calc.).	van't Hoff's coeff.	Degree of dissociation.
0.2700	0.08°	251	344	1.37	0.37

About 37% of the substance dissociates at the melting point of ice. Hence the ionisation constant, k , is equal to 6.8×10^{-3} . This is in fair agreement with the p_k value determined below.

Potentiometric Titration of the Complex Acid by Alkali

A definite weight of the substance was dissolved in conductivity water in a Jena flask to make 0.01 M solution; 125 c.c. of this solution were taken in a Jena beaker provided with an electrically driven stirrer. A glass electrode and a calomel electrode were dipped into the acid solution and the p_H of the solution was measured by a Beckman p_H meter, model 6. From a burette, small quantities of a strong alkali of known strength were added drop by drop with constant stirring and the p_H of the resulting solution measured. The total volume of the alkali added was too small to effect any appreciable volume change. Results are recorded in Table I below, and represented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

TABLE I

Alkali soln. = 0.42M.		$t = 26^\circ$.		Acid soln. = 0.01M.		
Alkali added.	Molar conc. of alkali.	p_H on rapid titration.	p_H after waiting for equilibrium.	pk_1 .	pk_2	\bar{n} .
0.0 c.c.	—	2.28	2.28	2.237	—	1.48
0.5	0.1674×10^{-2}	2.39	2.39	2.259	—	1.43
1.0	0.3348	2.57	2.57	2.367	—	1.40
1.5	0.5022	2.79	2.79	2.533	—	1.34
2.0	0.6696	3.18	3.18	2.735	—	1.26
2.5	0.8370	3.68	3.68	2.903	—	1.14
3.0	1.0044	4.45	3.90	—	6.367	1.00
3.5	1.1718	5.51	4.30	—	4.986	0.83
4.0	1.3392	8.30	4.00	—	4.891	0.66
4.5	1.5066	10.30	5.02	—	5.008	0.49
5.0	1.6740	10.73	5.49	—	5.274	0.32
5.5	1.8414	11.12	6.25	—	5.525	0.15
6.0	—	—	8.75	—	—	—
6.5	—	—	10.70	—	—	—

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

From Fig. 2 $pk_1 = 2.10$ ($k_1 = 7.94 \times 10^{-3}$); $pk_2 = 4.99$ ($k_2 = 1.02 \times 10^{-5}$)

Salts of the Monobasic Form of the Acid

Sodium Aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalate.—The sodium salt of the complex aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalic acid was prepared by the addition of sodium acetate dissolved in aqueous alcohol to that of the acid in molecular proportion. The sodium salt of the complex acid was thereby precipitated. This was then filtered on the pump, washed 4 to 5 times with 70% alcohol and then thoroughly with absolute alcohol. Finally, it was dried in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.

The substance forms brownish black crystals, highly soluble in water but insoluble in organic solvents. Its solution reacts acidic (p_H 4). It is stable in acid solution, but is readily decomposed by alkalis.

For analysis, the substance was treated with ammonia and hydrogen peroxide to convert the rhenium to perrhenate. The mixture was then acidified with HCl (conc.) and rhenium removed as Re_2S_7 . Sodium was then estimated as Na_2SO_4 in the filtrate. Rhenium was estimated as nitron perrhenate after the oxidation of Re_2S_7 with alkaline hydrogen peroxide. Oxalic acid was estimated in another sample of the substance by titration with permanganate after the removal of rhenium as ReO_2 by treatment with alkali as described before. {Found :

Re, 50.88; C_2O_4 , 24.08; Na, 6.31. $Na[Re.(OH)_3.C_2O_4.H_2O]$ requires Re, 50.95; C_2O_4 , 24.10; Na, 6.30 per cent]. The substance remains unchanged when dried at 110° - 115° .

Equivalent conductance.

	($t=25^{\circ}$)		
v (litres)	256	512	1024
Δv	81.85	97.81	110.3

Molecular conductance = 110.3 ohms⁻¹ (approx.)

Potassium aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by adding a solution of potassium acetate in alcohol to that of the complex acid in rectified spirit in equimolecular proportions. The potassium salt separated out from the solution. This was filtered, washed and dried as in the previous case.

The substance is insoluble in organic solvents, but highly soluble in water. {Found: Re, 48.74; C_2O_4 , 23.10; K, 10.21. $K[Re.(OH)_3.C_2O_4.H_2O]$ requires Re, 48.81; C_2O_4 , 23.10; K, 10.24 per cent}.

Thallium aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalate was obtained as a brown crystalline precipitate by adding a solution of the thallic sulphate in water to that of the complex rhenioxalic acid. This was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dried over concentrated sulphuric acid in a desiccator.

The substance is insoluble in water as well as in organic solvents, but is readily soluble in dilute mineral acids.

For analysis, the substance was treated with alkaline hydrogen peroxide to convert rhenium to perrhenate. From the solution rhenium was removed as Re_2S_7 as described before. In the filtrate thallium was precipitated as Tl_2S by treatment with H_2S in alkaline medium. The precipitate of Tl_2S was then dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid and thallium estimated as chromate from the solution.

Thallium was precipitated as $TlCl$ from another sample of the substance by means of HCl. In the filtrate oxalic acid was estimated as before, after the removal of rhenium as ReO_2 . {Found: Re, 30.45; C_2O_4 , 14.46; Tl, 33.50. $Tl[Re.(OH)_3.C_2O_4.H_2O]$, 3.5 H_2O requires Re, 30.54; C_2O_4 , 14.45; Tl, 33.50 per cent}.

Barium aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by double decomposition between barium chloride and the sodium aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalate in aqueous solution. The precipitated barium salt was washed thoroughly with water and then with a little alcohol. This was then dried in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.

The substance forms deep brown crystals insoluble in water and organic solvents, but readily soluble in mineral acids.

Barium was estimated as $BaSO_4$ from an acid solution of the substance. From the filtrate Re and oxalic acid were estimated as already described. {Found: Re, 40.82; C_2O_4 , 19.27; Ba, 15.08. $Ba[Re.(OH)_3.C_2O_4.H_2O]$, 5 H_2O requires Re, 40.83; C_2O_4 , 19.32; Ba, 15.04 per cent}.

Lead aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalate.—A solution of lead acetate in water was added drop by drop to an aqueous solution of the sodium aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalate. The lead salt separated out in the form of a grey crystalline powder. This was washed and dried as usual.

The lead salt is insoluble in water, but dissolves in dilute mineral acids.

Lead was estimated as $PbSO_4$ by digestion of the substance with dilute H_2SO_4 . Re and oxalic acid were estimated in the filtrate as usual. {Found: Re, 41.72; C_2O_4 , 19.72; Pb, 23.20. $Pb[Re.(OH)_3.C_2O_4.H_2O]$ requires Re, 41.75; C_2O_4 , 19.77; Pb, 23.23 per cent}.

Salts of the Dibasic Form of the Acid

Sodium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by the addition of an excess of sodium acetate to the aquo-trihydroxo complex acid in aqueous alcoholic solution. The sodium salt, which separated out, was filtered on the pump. This was dissolved in a little water and reprecipitated by the addition of sodium acetate solution in rectified spirit. It was then filtered, washed 4 to 5 times with 70% alcohol and then thoroughly with absolute alcohol. Finally, the product was dried in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.

The substance forms a grey crystalline powder, highly soluble in water but insoluble in organic solvents. The solution reacts almost neutral to litmus. It is stable in acid solution, but readily decomposes in alkali. {Found: Re, 43.82; C₂O₄, 20.71; Na, 10.85. Na₂[Re. (OH)₄. C₂O₄].2H₂O requires Re, 43.86; C₂O₄, 20.76; Na, 10.85 per cent.}

The two molecules of water could not be removed by drying even at 110°-115°.

Magnetic susceptibility.—The susceptibility was measured in a Gouy's balance. $\chi_g = -0.00938 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = -3.98 \times 10^{-6}$.

Cryoscopic measurements.—The molecular weight of the disodium salt was determined by lowering of the freezing-point method.

Substance (on anhydrous basis, g./25 c.c.)	Depression Δt .	M. W. (found).	M. W. (calc.).	vant Hoff's coeff.	Degree of dissociation.
0.0915	0.04°	164.7	388	2.36	0.68

The result shows that only about 68% of the salt appears to dissociate at the melting point of ice. This abnormally low value suggests its dimeric character.

Equivalent conductance measurement.

$$t = 25^\circ.$$

v (litres)	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Δ_p	51.90	52.65	67.10	72.10	79.60	89.0	105.15

Molecular conductance = 210.3 ohms⁻¹ (approx.).

Potassium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by the action of an alcoholic solution of potassium acetate on that of the complex rhenioxalic acid in water. The compound precipitated out completely by the addition of a further amount of alcohol. It was filtered, dissolved in water and reprecipitated by the addition of alcohol. This was again filtered, dissolved in water and reprecipitated by the addition of a concentrated solution of potassium acetate in alcohol. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with rectified spirit and then with absolute alcohol and finally dried in a desiccator over sulphuric acid.

The substance forms dark brown crystals, highly soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents. {Found: Re, 37.62; C₂O₄, 17.84; K, 15.82. K₂[Re.(OH)₄.C₂O₄].4H₂O requires Re, 37.80; C₂O₄, 17.89; K, 15.85 per cent.}

Ammonium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared exactly like the potassium salt using ammonium acetate in place of potassium acetate. The substance forms a brown powder, highly soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents. {Found: Re, 42.02; C₂O₄, 19.93; NH₄, 8.23. (NH₄)₂[Re.(OH)₄.C₂O₄]. 3.5H₂O requires Re, 42.18; C₂O₄, 19.95; NH₄, 8.16 per cent.}

Lithium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by the action of lithium carbonate on the acid. An alcoholic solution of lithium carbonate was added drop by drop with constant stirring to an aqueous solution of the complex aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalic acid. The mixture was allowed to stand for 15 minutes and the lithium salt was then precipitated by the addition of a further quantity of alcohol. This was filtered, dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and again reprecipitated by the addition of a concentrated solution of lithium carbonate in alcohol. The product was washed free from Li_2CO_3 with alcohol and then dried in a desiccator over sulphuric acid.

The substance forms deep brown crystals, soluble in water and also to some extent in aqueous alcohol, but insoluble in absolute alcohol and dioxane.

This was analysed like the corresponding sodium or potassium salt and lithium was estimated as Li_2SO_4 . {Found : Re, 40.05; C_2O_4 , 18.93; Li, 2.97; Li $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$, $6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Re, 40.09; C_2O_4 , 18.96; Li, 2.99 per cent}.

Barium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was obtained as a brown precipitate by the addition of an aqueous solution of barium chloride to that of the corresponding sodium salt. This was filtered, washed and dried as usual.

The substance forms brown crystals insoluble in water, but soluble in dilute mineral acids. {Found : Re, 38.73; C_2O_4 , 18.32; Ba, 28.62. Ba $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$ requires Re, 38.83; C_2O_4 , 18.37; Ba, 28.92 per cent}.

Calcium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by the addition of calcium chloride solution to that of the disodium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate. The precipitated calcium salt was washed and dried as in the previous cases. It resembles the barium salt in its properties.

For analysis, rhenium was first removed as Re_2S_7 in the manner described for the analysis of the thallium salt of the monobasic acid. In the filtrate from Re_2S_7 , calcium was precipitated as calcium oxalate and estimated volumetrically. Rhenium was estimated from the precipitated Re_2S_7 as nitron perrhenate.

From another sample, rhenium was precipitated as ReO_2 by alkalis. The mixture was then acidified to dissolve any precipitate of calcium oxalate. In the filtrate from ReO_2 , oxalic acid was estimated volumetrically after precipitation as calcium oxalate. {Found : Re, 48.46; C_2O_4 , 23.02; Ca, 10.47. Ca $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$ requires Re, 48.69; C_2O_4 , 23.03; Ca, 10.47 per cent}.

Strontium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by double decomposition between strontium chloride and the disodium rhenioxalate as in the case of the calcium salt.

Strontium was estimated as SrSO_4 after the precipitation of Re as Re_2S_7 .

Oxalic acid was estimated in another sample as described in the case of the calcium salt above. [Found : Re, 43.29; C_2O_4 , 20.48; Sr, 20.39. Sr $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$ requires Re, 43.30; C_2O_4 , 20.48; Sr, 20.39 per cent}.

Lead Tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate.—When a solution of lead acetate in water was added dropwise to an aqueous solution of the complex sodium salt, the insoluble lead salt separated out in the form of a grey crystalline powder. This was washed and dried as usual. {Found : Re, 33.87; C_2O_4 , 16.03; Pb, 37.74. Pb $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$ requires Re, 33.88; C_2O_4 , 16.03; Pb, 37.70 per cent}.

Copper Tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate.—A solution of copper acetate in rectified spirit was added to an aqueous solution of the complex acid. The mixture was allowed to stand for a while when a grey precipitate settled down. This was filtered, washed and dried as usual.

The substance is slightly soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents. When decomposed with alkali, the substance gives first a yellow precipitate and on heating on the

water-bath the yellow precipitate turns chocolate-brown. Cupric ion in solution was therefore reduced to the cuprous state by the quadrivalent rhenium and the cuprous tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was precipitated.

For analysis, the substance was treated with alkaline hydrogen peroxide. The precipitated copper oxide was filtered and estimated iodometrically. Rhenium was estimated in the filtrate as usual.

Oxalic acid was estimated as in the case of calcium or strontium salt after the removal of rhenium as ReO_2 . {Found: Re, 38.91; C_2O_4 , 18.41; Cu, 26.57. $\text{Cu}_2[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$, 0.5 H_2O requires Re, 38.91; C_2O_4 , 18.41; Cu, 26.57 per cent}.

Zinc tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate.—Zinc acetate was dissolved in rectified spirit and was added to the aqueous solution of the complex acid, when the zinc salt of the acid separated out. This was washed thoroughly first with dilute alcohol and then with absolute alcohol and finally dried as before.

The substance forms a grey crystalline powder, slightly soluble in water, and insoluble in organic solvents.

Zinc was estimated as zinc ammonium phosphate after the removal of rhenium as Re_2S_7 , as described before.

Oxalic acid was also estimated in the manner described for the calcium salt. {Found: Re, 40.37; C_2O_4 , 19.09; Zn, 14.17. $\text{Zn}[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$, 3 H_2O requires Re, 40.31; C_2O_4 , 19.07; Zn, 14.17 per cent}.

Cadmium tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by adding a solution of cadmium acetate in rectified spirit to an aqueous solution of the complex aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalic acid. The precipitated cadmium salt was filtered and again digested with cadmium acetate solution in rectified spirit. The product was washed and dried as usual. It resembles the zinc salt in properties.

Cadmium was estimated as cadmium oxinate after the removal of rhenium as Re_2S_7 .

Rhenium and oxalic acid were estimated as in the case of the zinc or calcium salt. {Found: Re, 39.31; C_2O_4 , 18.57; Cd, 23.82. $\text{Cd}[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$, H_2O requires Re, 39.37; C_2O_4 , 18.65; Cd, 23.79 per cent}.

Nickel tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate.—Nickel acetate was dissolved in rectified spirit and was added drop by drop to an aqueous solution of the aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalic acid with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for a while when the nickel salt separated out in the form of a grey crystalline powder. This was washed and dried as usual.

The process of analysis resembled that of the zinc or cadmium salt, nickel being estimated as nickel dimethylglyoxime. {Found: Re, 42.59; C_2O_4 , 20.16; Ni, 13.49. $\text{Ni}[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$, 2 H_2O requires Re, 42.59; C_2O_4 , 20.15; Ni, 13.48 per cent}.

Cobalt tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by the action of cobalt acetate on the complex acid as described in the case of the nickel salt.

The substance forms a deep brown crystalline powder, soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents.

The method of analysis was similar to that employed for the nickel salt, cobalt being estimated as CoSO_4 . {Found: Re, 44.35; C_2O_4 , 20.93; Co, 14.05. $\text{Co}[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$, H_2O requires Re, 44.40; C_2O_4 , 21.00; Co, 14.06 per cent}.

Hexamine tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate was prepared by adding an excess of hexamethylenetetramine solution in alcohol to an alcoholic solution of the complex aquo-trihydroxo rhenioxalic acid. The substance separated out in the form of a black crystalline powder. The product was redissolved in a little water, filtered to separate any ReO_2 formed, and repre-

cipitated by the addition of alcohol. This was washed and dried as usual. The substance is highly soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's process. {Found : Re, 35.76 ; C_2O_4 , 16.96 ; N, 10.75. $(CH_2)_6N_4$, $H_2[Re.(OH)_4.C_2O_4]$, $2H_2O$ requires Re, 35.78 ; C_2O_4 , 16.92 ; N_2 , 10.78 per cent}.

Strychnine tetrahydroxo rhenioxalate.—Strychnine acetate was dissolved in alcohol and was added drop by drop with constant stirring to an alcoholic solution of the complex acid. The strychnine salt separating was redissolved in a little water and reprecipitated by the addition of an alcoholic solution of strychnine acetate, washed and dried as usual. The substance forms a dark grey crystalline powder, insoluble in organic solvents, but soluble in water.

Rhenium was estimated as nitron perrhenate after removal as Re_2S_7 in the manner described before. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. {Found : Re, 16.58 ; C, 47.06 ; N, 5.00. $(C_{21}H_{22}O_2N_2)_2$, $H_2[Re.(OH)_4.C_2O_4]$, $6H_2O$ requires Re, 16.61 ; C, 47.14 ; N, 5.00 per cent}.

With silver salt solutions rhenioxalic acid and its salts are oxidised to give perrhenic acid or perrhenates, and silver is reduced to the metallic state.

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